

Deliverable 2.2.2.1

DATA ON POLICY SUPPORT FOR RENEWABLE ELECTRICITY AND
ELECTRIC VEHICLES (VERSION 1, FEBRUARY 2025)

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Data on policy support for renewable electricity and electric vehicles (Version 1, February 2025)

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General Information

Summary

There is a need for detailed, empirical research to investigate how policies impact the trajectory of energy transitions. However, research is often held back by a lack of data, especially machine-readable data, on such policies. There are generally a few types of data that can be used to investigate the transition: datasets counting the number of policies over time, datasets that provide detailed information on a single policy instrument such as carbon pricing, and case studies of specific countries and their policies. While these datasets have some benefits, they cannot be combined and are either insufficiently detailed or insufficiently broad to address research questions such as how effective policies are in promoting the energy transition, or to more effectively model transition dynamics.

In order to enable cross-country analyses of the effectiveness of different policy instruments, we create a detailed, machine-readable dataset of energy policies that support renewable electricity and electric vehicle adoption. To do so, we build on existing datasets as well as desktop research. An important part of this work was developing a methodology and data infrastructure to standardize how policies are recorded, enabling future researchers to record data in a way that is interoperable with our own data as well as that of existing datasets. This also includes the work to build a policy ontology in NFDI Measure 4.5. Further details on our data collection methods and process are included in the Metadata document.

The present dataset focuses on support policies for renewable electricity and electric vehicles in four countries (Germany, France, Ireland and Greece). This relatively narrow focus allows us to go into great detail on a broad range of policy instruments, show that the ontological work for climate policies done in NFDI4Energy works for actual data gathering, and to establish and test a robust data-gathering protocol which will be used to expand the country focus in the future.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

This deliverable is part of Measure 2.2 (Energy policy regulation, political preferences, and logics), with two main deliverables (see below).

- D2.2.1.1 Data on landscape and environmental regulations for energy production and infrastructure
- D2.2.2.1 Data on policy support (this deliverable)
- D2.2.2.2 Data on climate and renewable electricity targets

The main tasks in this deliverable were collecting time-series data on policy support for renewable energy technologies and electric vehicles. The collected data should serve as an input for the energy research community, but also within NFDI for TA4 to ensure appropriate metadata standards and domain-specific ontologies.

Within TA4, the tasks are related to both the metadata schema (Measure 4.3 Development of metadata standards for energy research data) and energy policy ontologies (Measure 4.5 Policy ontology).

Measure 4.5 was based on our work in this deliverable, as we discovered on beginning the research that there was a need for a policy ontology because of the different ways that research data on policy instruments were collected, lacking interoperability. We see this deliverable as tightly linked to Measure 4.5 as it is both a use case for the policy ontology, and a test of how robust this ontology is.

In addition, the data gathered here will be used to inform holistic energy modeling in M2.4, especially how policy support interacts with public acceptance and policy logics.

Related deliverables and measures in NFDI4Energy: D2.2.1.1, D2.2.2.2, Measure 2.4, 4.3 and 4.5.

Figure 1: Links between measures within Task Area 2 and other Task Areas.

Introduction

To achieve the temperature targets of the Paris Agreement, a comprehensive transition across multiple sectors, including the energy sector, to a zero-carbon state is necessary. One way to address this problem is to develop interdisciplinary energy models for guiding the low-carbon transition, as discussed in [1, 2]. However, many empirical analyses overlook integrating socio-political factors, resulting in inaccurate modeling results and future plans. One possible reason for not including social and political factors is the lack of openly accessible, machine-readable datasets on energy policy [3].

This lack of machine-readable data also makes it difficult to systematically analyze which policies and combinations of policies are the best to quickly reduce emissions. Presently, there is no comprehensive data on this, so empirical analysis is difficult: often, we do not systematically know what the effects of policy instrument really are. Researchers who try to answer climate and energy policy research questions are usually forced to use proxies for policy ambition and effectiveness for their analyses, such as count variables for the number of policies passed per year rather than what these policies *actually do*. This is because existing datasets with information on support policies are insufficient in terms of the scope that would be needed to accurately model the role of policy in the transition. Here, we provide a brief outline of the kinds of data that are available.

First, there are datasets **identifying climate policies across countries, sectors, and time**, such as Climate Policy Database or Climate Policy Radar (which also draw from sources like the International Energy Agency, IEA). The advantage of such datasets is that they allow researchers to explore policies in many different countries. The disadvantage is that they are generally insufficiently detailed, as one single policy may contain many different instruments and they cannot have the level of detail needed to accurately assess ambition. For example, that a policy exists is important information, but without knowing its support level, ambition, and mode of operation, further and more useful analyses are often impossible. In addition, as we show below, these existing datasets do not provide an exhaustive list of all policies. These datasets are also not interoperable as they use different typologies of policy instruments (see NFDI deliverable 4.5.1.1, Policy Ontology Draft). Often researchers use this data by creating a count variable of how many policies existed per year to create a proxy for ambition, as using this data for more precise analyses is not possible in most cases [4].

Second, there are datasets that provide a detailed overview of **a single (energy) policy instrument across countries and time**, such as the AURES dataset which has information on auctions of renewable energy capacity, or the World Bank Carbon Pricing Dashboard.¹ While these are very helpful for learning about a specific instrument, they are not interoperable with each other, and one can therefore not compare the effectiveness of these instruments and how they interact. In addition, the AURES project has finished in 2021 and the data are no longer being updated. To the best of our knowledge, there are no specific datasets on individual EV support policies.

Finally, there are **case studies** of specific countries and their policies to enable analyses of policy effectiveness. For these, authors gathered detailed data for themselves which is not often published openly. Even if this data is made publicly available, it is in whatever format the authors found appropriate for their analysis, and is therefore not interoperable with other datasets and cannot be used for analyses. These data are usually gathered on the author's specific area of expertise, which tends to be highly disciplinary and not necessarily intersectoral.

There are several challenges to gathering detailed time-series and machine-readable data on policies from multiple sectors. These challenges include but are not limited to:

¹ <https://carbonpricingdashboard.worldbank.org/>

- **Policy complexity:** Policies often include many different conditions which are not easily understandable, and very difficult to record in a machine-readable manner.
- **Policy changes:** Policies are constantly being updated and modified, which necessitates constant updates to ensure that the data are accurate.
- **Language barriers:** Policies are written in complex language, and while automatic translation software such as DeepL have greatly improved in the past years, there are still difficult nuances which take time to untangle and cross-check.
- **Sectoral barriers:** Researchers tend to work on a specific area (for example, power generation) and may therefore only gather more detailed data on their area of expertise (solar and wind). This means that there are no detailed datasets that address multiple sectors such as transport and electricity generation.
- **Process barriers:** There is no agreed-upon standard for how to record details of often very complex policies in a machine-readable way. For example, every researcher and database uses different terms and definitions for policy instruments.
- **Time and resource barriers:** The amount of person-hours that it takes to create a protocol for data collection and then collect this data in the necessary depth and breadth is very high. In addition, data collection requires a sufficient degree of familiarity with both policy instruments and the subject of the policy support (in this case vehicles and/or renewable power).

To address this gap, we have developed a method to gather detailed policy data, and have begun to gather time-series datasets of climate and energy policies for different European countries under NFDI4Energy Measure 2.2 (Energy policy regulation, political preferences, and logics), which include renewable energy and electric vehicle support policies, decarbonization targets (e.g., carbon emissions and renewable electricity targets), and energy infrastructure regulation.

This deliverable focuses on support policies for renewable energy and electric vehicles. Our detailed policy support data enables comparisons between countries and years in detail for Germany, France, Greece and Ireland. We also establish a data-gathering protocol that enables future researchers to systematically gather data which can be combined with ours, enhancing the coverage of this work. Our data are published in time-series, machine-readable formats under FAIR principles. This will enable researchers to test hypotheses about policy effectiveness, and to incorporate data on policies into models.

Introduction to the Datasets

The Renewable Power and EV support datasets contain detailed, machine-readable data on support policies for renewable energy and electric vehicles from the years 2000-2024 for Germany, Greece, Ireland, and France. The data are derived from publicly available sources.

For renewable electricity support policies, the main source upon which our dataset builds is “The global renewable power support dataset” [5]. The data from this source go up until 2016 and in some cases 2017. We make a number of changes to this dataset and its structure to make it machine-readable and more easily accessible (further information on these changes is found in the Metadata document). In addition, we conduct further research on renewable energy to complete the dataset until the present.

We also gather data on electric vehicle support policies from 2000-2024. This was done using publicly available sources including Climate Policy Radar, Climate Policy Database, the IEA, RES-legal.eu, World Bank, OECD, IRENA, relevant national ministries, industry bodies, and other websites. Information about the source of each individual observation can be found in the column “source”. Data from secondary sources include original source URLs, some of which are no longer valid. When possible, we have replaced these broken links with the archived version from the Internet Archive

Wayback Machine. Note that some data for 2024 (especially on auctions and tenders) may not yet be complete, and should only be used with caution until further updates are finished.

The datasets focus on national policy instruments and do not include higher-level policies like the EU level or lower-level policies like the federal states or cities. This version of the data focuses on Germany, France, Ireland and Greece as test cases for the ontology and data-gathering method. We intend to expand it to future countries in the near future.

The dataset covers policies that support renewable electricity and the use of electric and plug-in hybrid vehicles. The following technologies are included:

Data type	Technologies included
Renewable electricity generation	Bioenergy CSP Wind (onshore and offshore) PV (on building and field)
Electric vehicles	Plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEV) Battery electric vehicles (EV) Charging infrastructure

We also record information on policies when they apply to multiple different kinds of technologies. For example, some vehicle support policies technically apply to all vehicles, but only those with lower emissions levels receive benefits (which tend to be EVs and PHEVs). We focus on passenger cars, but also record information on support schemes to encourage the use of electric passenger vehicles by companies and local government, but this is not the focus of our work. More details on how specific instances are coded can be found in the Metadata document.

Approach to gathering policy data

General approach

During the process of collecting and cleaning data for this project, we took an iterative approach to structuring the information we presented. From the outset we had a structure for the data recording format, but this often ran into the reality of very complex policies. We therefore had to refine our approach during the data-gathering process.

For example, we originally hoped to record the support levels for specific technologies, such as:

- FIT for solar PV = EUR 0.05 per kWh
- FIT for onshore wind = EUR 0.05 per kWh
- Auction with FIT for offshore wind = EUR 0.03 per kWh
- Auction with FIT for onshore wind = EUR 0.04 per kWh...

However, policies in the real world are rarely (if ever) this simple. Usually they have different conditions, such as:

- FIT for Solar PV building-integrated, size between 2 and 50 kW = EUR 0.05 per kWh
- FIT for Solar PV, building-integrated, size between 51 and 100 kW = EUR 0.04 per kWh

An example of what this looks like in practice is the following text that determines the amount of EV purchasing bonuses under French law (translated with DeepL):

“For vehicles... whose carbon dioxide emission rate is less than or equal to 116 grams per kilometer, classified as “electric” or “1”, or “2” registered after September 1, 2019 and not previously registered for the first time in France or abroad...

a) The amount of aid is set at 1,500 euros within the limit of the acquisition cost of the vehicle including all taxes, if the vehicle is acquired or leased by a natural person whose reference tax income per share is less than or equal to 13,489 euros;

(b) The amount of aid is set at 80% of the purchase price, up to a limit of EUR 3,000, if the vehicle is acquired or leased either by a natural person whose reference tax income per share is less than or equal to EUR 13,489 and whose distance between home and workplace is greater than 30 kilometres or who travels more than 12,000 kilometres per year as part of their professional activity with their personal vehicle, or by a natural person whose reference tax income per share is less than or equal to EUR 6,300”

Therefore, we had to create ways to record data with multiple conditions that need to be fulfilled in order to receive support. For more information on our approach to this issue, see section “Conditions and support levels” and the accompanying metadata.

In other cases, policy instruments covered multiple technologies: for example, there are examples of auctions with FIT that are for both solar and wind without information on whether there are differences in the support amount offered for specific technologies. In order to express this in a machine-readable way, we had to create a “multiple technologies” category and a column in which to record which kinds of technologies are covered.

Another example related to auctions was that we needed to make decisions on what information to record in complex cases, and then record this as a protocol to follow in future cases. For example, some auctions have different levels of support in different regions (for example, northern vs southern Germany). We took the average of the support levels for these regional rates, and will do so in the future. Countries also differentiate support levels and price caps depending on installation age, which we decided to record as follows:

- **Bioenergy:** in Germany, there are different prices and caps for older versus new biomass installations. So far, Germany has only awarded capacities to these older installations, so we only record the support level for older installations. If there are cases in the future where support is awarded to both older and newer installations, we will continue to record only the support level for older installations to ensure this is comparable with previous observations.
- **Onshore wind repowering:** in some countries, there are different support levels repowering versus other onshore wind (for example in Italy, from 2020 onwards). However, only new capacity has been awarded support. We therefore record only auction results for new capacity. If there are cases where both repowered and new auctions are awarded for onshore wind, we will continue to take the support levels and conditions for new-build onshore wind to ensure this is comparable with previous observations.

There are many further examples of these kinds of decisions which are explained in the Metadata document. The detailed documentation and established procedure are important for research data transparency, and can provide a helpful protocol for future researchers gathering information on energy and climate policies.

Compatibility with existing datasets: IEA, CPDB and CPR

As we began to create a protocol to gather data for the RE power dataset updates and EV data, we drew from existing datasets that gather policy information: the IEA, CPDB and CPR.

Our original goal was to ensure complete interoperability with these datasets; this proved to be impossible because we identified many policies and policy instruments that were not collected by other sources. For example: for Ireland, we found policy instruments for EV support within 18 different national budgets and finance acts. CPR only records 3 national budgets or finance documents that are coded as impacting transport, the IEA records 1, and CPDB records 1. This also clearly demonstrates the need for more detailed policy data, as the existing coverage is insufficient.

In addition, the datasets all have different definitions for the kinds of policy instruments they record, which is an issue when it comes to measuring instrument coverage in-depth [4]. As part of our work in gathering data we therefore develop an interoperable policy typology, described in NFDI Deliverable 4.5.1.1, “Draft Policy Ontology”. The ontology combines definitions from the Open Energy Ontology (OEO), and typologies that institutions use to gather climate policy data from Climate Policy Database (CPDB) and Climate Policy Radar (CPR). This was further complemented by a preliminary academic literature review and input from climate policy researchers. At the time of writing this document, we are validating, cross-checking and, wherever needed or helpful, updating it through a systematic literature review. The data-gathering process and policy ontology serve as test cases for the validity of this approach.

A further challenge for interoperability is the structure of existing databases. The CPR and IEA use policy titles, which also differ greatly between datasets, and do not use a policy identifier number. Helpfully, the CPDB uses a policy identifier number which means that we can match our policy instruments with their observation numbers. We therefore include a CPDB identifier number for equivalent observations in our dataset. We also create our own identifier number so that future researchers can easily match our observations with their own, and more easily communicate if they wish to provide feedback.

Policy instruments and policy change

For policy support data, our focus is on public policies, which we define as “efforts made by governments to alter aspects of their own or social behavior in order to carry out some end or purpose and are comprised of complex arrangements of policy goals and policy means” [6, p. 282].

In terms of policy means, we look at policy instruments: the specific policy measures by which the government aims to achieve its objectives. Within this category, we have gathered information on both economic and regulatory instruments. We define an economic instrument is a policy instrument that hands out or takes away material resources while the addressees are not obligated to take the measures involved [7]. At this time, we do not gather data on information policy instruments or voluntary policy instruments. The way policy instruments are defined and relate to each other is explained in NFDI4Energy Deliverable 4.5.1.1 (Draft Policy Ontology Report).

For electric vehicle support policy instruments, we focus on 11 instruments which influence the uptake of electric vehicles. We include both policy instruments that support EV purchasing and EV charging. A list of the relevant policy instruments and their short descriptions is below.

Table 1: Summary of recorded policy instruments for electric vehicle adoption support

Economic instruments	
Policy instrument name	Definition
Subsidy	A grant where the government pays part of the cost of an investment or activity, decreasing the amount paid by investors. For EVs, we record 2 sub-types: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Product purchase subsidies - Project subsidies

Tax incentives	A fiscal incentive where the government reduces or exempts taxes for selected activities or actors, with the purpose of incentivizing mitigation activities. For EVs, we record 2 sub-types: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tax reductions - Tax exemptions
Feebate	A feebate or bonus-malus scheme imposes additional fees on a high-emitting technology and provides rebates for low-emitting technologies. An emissions “null-point” is set, where the buyer gets neither a bonus nor a malus. The idea is that the system would be neutral on public finances.
Soft loan	Loans provided by the government or a government body with preferential conditions to lower financing costs
Tender with support	Government tenders for which investors put bids, which may be awarded some amount of support. For example, a government may publish a tender for the construction of 6,000 EV charging points and then award contracts to companies with favorable conditions.
Product retirement premium	A retirement premium for emissions-intensive products used by consumers such as fossil fuel vehicle swap or scrappage schemes.
Fee decreases or exemptions	Fiscal incentives where the government supports mitigation activities by reducing or exempting green activities from existing fees or charges (such as exempting EVs from paying highway tolls).
Regulatory instruments	
User change	A regulatory instrument that fosters changes in user behavior, for example reduction of available parking places.
Technology standard	A regulatory instrument that requires a specific technology, process or product. This can include phase-out mandates or bans of polluting technologies like ICE vehicles.

For renewable electricity support policy instruments, we focus on 10 specific economic instruments which influence the expansion of renewable electricity generation. Some instruments, such as emissions trading, which target both the power and other sectors and therefore may indirectly impact the competitiveness of renewable power vs fossil fuels are also included. A list of the relevant policy instruments and their short descriptions is below (more details can be found in the respective sections).

Table 2 Summary of recorded policy instruments for renewable electricity adoption support

Policy instrument name	Description
Feed-in tariff (FIT)	Renewable power generators are paid a fixed sum of money for energy fed into the grid, for a number of years into the future.
Feed-in premium	Renewable power generators are paid a premium on top of the price they achieve in the general electricity market, for electricity fed into the grid, for a number of years into the future.
Subsidy	A grant where the government pays part of the cost of an investment or activity, decreasing the amount paid by investors.
Accelerated depreciation	Altered financial rules for renewable power projects, allowing them to depreciate (part of) the investment in the early years of the asset’s life.
Emissions trading	Emissions trading indirectly supports renewable power, as it makes carbon-intensive power generation relatively more expensive. We record two subtypes, voluntary and cap-and-trade.
Soft loan	Loans provided by the government or a government body with preferential conditions to lower financing costs

Loan guarantee	Governments seek to reduce the financing costs of new projects by guaranteeing to pay the loan should the project go bankrupt.
Tax incentives	Tax incentives refer to tax rebates for renewables (e.g. a VAT reduction for renewable power projects). These may be either tax exemptions or reductions.
Auction with FIT or FIP	Governments put out tenders for specific amounts of capacity (or energy), to which investors put bids, which are awarded a fixed tariff or a premium for a number of years.
Tradeable green certificates (TGC)	The government sets a long-term goal and yearly trajectory for the share of renewable power, and mandates all suppliers to obtain and surrender certificates each year as proof that they have bought sufficient amounts of renewables in their power mix. These certificates can be traded, providing an additional income for the producer.

We also record detailed information on how policy instruments changed over time in two columns. In one we record whether the policy instrument changed (yes or no), and in the other we record details on the precise change. This allows users to quickly identify events and their importance within the dataset, while maintaining machine-readability.

Conditions and support levels

Many policies have conditions about what support levels different technologies are eligible for. For example, some countries only provide FITs for installations under a certain size; or they have different subsidy rates for smaller or larger businesses. We illustrate how these conditions work with 3 cases.

Case 1: One condition. A country will only grant its FIT of EUR 0.06 per kW to solar PV installations up to 100 kW in size. This would be recorded as follows:

Tech_type	Condition_max_1	Condition_unit_1	level_1	level_1_currency	level_1_unit
solar PV	100	kW	0.06	EUR	kW

Case 2: Different group conditions. A country has multiple conditions, so that different groups receiving different levels of support. For example, a country may have many possible levels of FIT for different sizes of installations: EUR 0.06 for installations under 100 kW, or EUR 0.04 for installations between 100-300 kW, etc. This would be recorded as follows:

Condition_min_1	Condition_max_1	Condition_unit_1	lvl_1	lvl_1_currency	lvl_1_unit	Condition_min_2	Condition_max_2	Condition_unit_2	lvl_2	lvl_2_currency
NA	100	kW	0.06	EUR	kW	100	300	kW	0.04	EUR

Case 3: Multiple conditions. Another possibility is that to receive a subsidy, several different conditions must all be fulfilled. Taking the example of purchase subsidies for plug-in hybrid vehicles in France, the vehicles must fulfill BOTH these conditions if they are to receive the EUR 2000 purchase bonus:

- Condition 1: Vehicle price of EUR 50,000 or less, AND
- Condition 2: Vehicle range of 50 km

We record this as in the table below. The level of support is only recorded in level_1, and level_2 is left blank. Details on the unit (i.e. EUR vehicle price, km vehicle range) are recorded in the sections Condition_1_notes and Condition_2_notes.

Condition_min_1	Condition_max_1	Condition_unit_1	lvl_1	lvl_1_currency	Condition_min_2	Condition_max_2	Condition_unit_2
NA	50000	EUR	2000	EUR	50	NA	km

Multiple_conditions_attributes: To signal to the data user the difference between Case 2 (different levels of support for different groups) and Case 3 (conditions that must all be met to receive support), we fill in the cell “Multiple_conditions_attribute”. Case 2 would be filled in as GROUP and case 3 as ALL. For Case 1, this column is marked NA (not applicable).

Multiple_conditions_attribute	<p>The condition attribute applies when the policy has multiple conditions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GROUP: Each regulation condition applies separately, such as different levels of subsidies for different emissions thresholds - All: All conditions of apply together, and if you do not meet all conditions you do not receive support.
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So far, we have collected data by adding instrument conditions and levels as needed: most do not have more than 2, and very few have more than 5. However, there are some exceptions for this, such as the French Feebate scheme for electric vehicles. While it began in 2008 with 4 vehicle classes with different fees and rebates depending on their emissions intensity, by 2021 there were 72 vehicle classes [8]. We therefore record this as follows:

- Condition_1: the lowest value of all the classes
- Condition_2: the value for which there is neither a fee nor a levy
- Condition_3: the highest value for all the classes.

In the policy instruments described above, support levels are determined by setting a specific currency price per unit. Monetary data usually represents the support paid per unit during a calendar year. Entries that concern monetary support are recorded as listed in the source, which is usually the local currency. We include both currency values for the year in which they are listed, and a column with these values transformed into USD to more easily compare across time and countries. To do so we use the World Bank yearly exchange rates, for each year. Note that all monetary data are nominal values, and need to be adjusted for inflation rates to convert them into real terms.

Other support instruments instead set a threshold of support. For example, in subsidy instruments the government may reimburse up to 30% of the total investment cost of an electric vehicle charging station. We would record this in the column “level_1_percent”, which is a numeric variable of the percent reimbursed.

measure	Tech_type	lvl_1	lvl_1_currency	level_1_percent	level_1_percent_type	level_1_percent_type_detail
subsidy	Charging infrastructure	NA	NA	30	Project and Investment Costs	% total cost

We also record details on the percentage type with the language from the policy. For ease of interpretation, we also code a “level_1_percentage_type” variable which broadly categorizes what the support mechanism targets (Import taxes, Value-added and sales taxes, Operational costs, etc). More details on how this is coded are found in the Metadata document.

Some policies also determine the number of years that a project is eligible for support (for example a FIT is paid for 20 years). If this information is available, it is recorded under **support_duration**. A slightly different concept is the **cap** on how much support will be given. For example, some EV

bonuses are only granted to the first 200,000 vehicles to register; or wind power projects only receive the FIT rate for up to a certain amount of full-load hours. Grants and subsidies may also be capped at some percent of total investment. In some cases, we were able to find information that a cap exists but not the actual limits, which we therefore record in the column “cap_possible” as “yes”.

Finally, some policy support is subject to **degression**: This means that support levels decrease by a pre-determined rate. For example, a degression of 5% per year for a FIP means that the premium for new installations in year t+1 is 5% lower than for installations entering into operation in year t. If there is information on the degression, we record the unit and currency of this decrease.

Notes on renewable energy conditions

For electric vehicles, conditions are always coded according to the formal methodology laid out in the section “Support level and conditions” above. However, information renewable power conditions and levels derived from Hafner & Lilliestam (i.e. data until 2017) must be interpreted carefully for the values of 5 MW and 20 MW, as these may refer either to a size limitation, or to a indicative installation size. In the second case, this leaves the possibility that there are also other FIT levels for sizes such as 30 MW etc. which are not recorded. The authors did not indicate in the metadata which of the two interpretations is the right one.

In order to combine this data for analysis, users may transform it and take the average of all support levels for a given technology type across all recorded conditions. Below is a sample of illustration of what this could look like in practice; highlighted rows would be averaged.

year	Tech_type	C_min_1	C_max_1	C_unit_1	lvl_1	lvl_1_currency	lvl_1_unit	C_min_2	C_max_2	lvl_2	lvl_2_currency
2016	solar PV	NA	20	MW	0.03	EUR	kWh	NA	NA	NA	NA
2016	solar PV	NA	5	MW	0.05	EUR	kWh	NA	NA	NA	NA
2017	solar PV	NA	20	MW	0.03	EUR	kWh	NA	NA	NA	NA
2017	solar PV	NA	5	MW	0.05	EUR	kWh	NA	NA	NA	NA
2018	solar PV	1	5	MW	0.05	EUR	kWh	6	20	0.03	EUR
2019	solar PV	2	5	MW	0.04	EUR	kWh	6	20	0.04	EUR
2020	solar PV	2	10	MW	0.04	EUR	kWh	10	20	0.02	EUR

In the future, we plan to re-code the data by determining whether 5 MW and 20 MW values are all indicative of a support range, or whether they are indeed conditions, and adapt these data points to fit our approach in NFDI4Energy.

Method for gathering policy data

We use a slightly different method for the RE and EV policy support datasets, as the former is based on existing data while the latter is completely hand-gathered. These are explained below in detail.

Renewable power policy data

Our renewable energy power data are based on existing datasets, and desktop research.

Data from 2000-2016 are based on Hafner and Lilliestam (2019), “The global renewable power support dataset”, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3371375>. The policy data collection of Hafner & Lilliestam focused on a set of 10 economic policy support instruments for renewable electricity. All non-economic instruments, such as zoning, building or environmental regulations, and performance standards were excluded. The focus was purely on instruments that seek to either address the income (e.g. by creating an additional or fixed income level for operators) or expenditures side (e.g. subsidy to reduce investment size; soft loan to reduce the financing cost) of an investment in

renewable electricity. The data gathering was entirely manual, drawing first on existing but not machine-readable datasets such as the IEA policies database² and res-legal.eu.³ This data was then completed for all years, often drawing on primary resources (e.g. the laws and policies from each country) or on secondary literature (e.g. World Bank reports on climate policies of single countries). In addition, the authors searched the websites of the governments or relevant authorities of each country for additional support policies that were not included in other datasets, and to expand the dataset either for earlier or later years than covered in the datasets existing in 2016/17. During coding, authors also updated the instrument selection to correspond to the instrument types countries actually use, and to include the main attributes and characteristics of each instrument type. This way, authors were as certain as possible to complete the dataset for the 10 selected instrument types.

In NFDI4Energy, we cleaned this data and transformed it into a machine-readable format, debugged it and fixed identified errors. In addition to the data from Hafner & Lilliestam, we gather further information on these 10 policy instruments for the years 2017-2024. Our process for these updates is as follows.

First, we checked for additional data sources online that could be used to update their work which have coverage of our countries of interest: Germany, France, Ireland, and Greece. We found this for two policy instruments: emissions trading, and renewable energy auctions. AURES II (<http://aures2project.eu/>) gathers data on auctions in EU countries until 2021, and ICAP (<https://icapcarbonaction.com/en>) gathers data on emissions trading for all countries (current to 2025). This was cleaned and read into our dataset, and updated if possible.

Next, we manually updated the remaining years (i.e. tenders from 2021-present) and instruments (accelerated depreciation, FITs, FIPs, soft loans, loan guarantees, tax incentives, subsidies, and TGCs). This was done with the following process:

- Checking the link/source from Hafner and Lilliestam for previous observations, and continuing using this source
- If the source no longer existed or was no longer being updated, establishing an overview of which policies are likely to be in force in each country in the IEA and Climate Policy Database. This allowed us to look closely at new laws and regulations passed by the government that could have influenced the existence of policy instruments and their level of support.
- Searching the websites of relevant national institutions for further details on specific policy instruments (i.e. in the case of loans in Germany, the website of the KfW; or the national Irish budget which is published on the government website yearly).
- In some cases where information was difficult to find, we also looked at the websites and reports of industry associations, such as the French solar association: <https://franceterritoiresolaire.fr/>.

EV policy data

In order to collect data on EV policy support instruments, we first collected data from existing sources on policies that support changes to decarbonize transportation from Climate Policy Database, Climate Policy Radar, and the IEA. These recorded policies were then examined in detail to determine the precise instruments and scope.

² <https://www.iea.org/policies>

³ <http://www.res-legal.eu/home/>

We chose to focus only on certain instruments that directly support higher EV or PHEV adoption. In addition, we exclude policy instruments that support uptake of only hybrid vehicles (that are not plug-in hybrid) or hydrogen vehicles, which could by some definitions also be seen as “electric”. We also do not look at instruments that support heavy trucks, buses, scooters, e-bikes, taxis or limousines, and service vehicles. In some cases, such as Germany, there are additional policy instruments to support the leasing of electric vehicles; these are also excluded, as they do not relate to purchasing new vehicles.

We then cross-checked the remaining policies from CPDB, CPR and IEA with reports from industry on policies to support electric vehicles. The European Automobile Manufacturers Association (ACEA) has published reports on vehicle taxes since 2001 which include detailed information on taxes and fees for vehicle acquisition and ownership. In some cases, countries have included incentives such as tax exemptions and rebates for EVs which are not always picked up in every database because they are not part of the official national climate policies but rather national tax codes or budgets. This enables us to flag additional policy instruments that we should collect data on. We also cross-check our policy instruments with the ACEA EV support policy factsheets which are published yearly with specific information for electric vehicles.

After establishing the list of policy instruments, we perform detailed desktop research to record the precise levels and conditions of policy support. We begin from the link or policy name given by the respective source (CPDB, CPR, IEA, ACEA) and seek the specific law, regulation or related document published by the government or other state authority. As many links are out of date, especially for older policies, we also use the Wayback machine. Whenever possible, we identify the original document that is the basis for the policy support and link to this in the column “source”. If this is not possible, we link to secondary sources such as government reports on the policy.

So far, this approach has resulted in us identifying 11 policy instruments for EV policy support which are relevant in France, Germany, Greece and Ireland. In upcoming updates we will add further countries and, to the extent useful or necessary, further instruments.

Additional variables recorded in the EV dataset

Because our data collection method is slightly different to the RE dataset, we have some variables which differ from the RE power dataset. These are as follows:

Policy publication information: We record information on when policy instruments – or changes to policy instruments – were published, implemented, and ended. We also include information on the intended end date of an instrument, if this is included in the document. This allows us to track changes over time in the policies themselves, and changes to the original plans.

Policy instrument subtype: In some cases, we include information on the policy instrument subtype to make the data more easily understandable for a human reader. This is most important for tax incentives. Details on the policy instrument subtype are recorded in the column “Instrument_subtype”.

Name: In column “name” we also record the name of the policy or policy document where the benefits are granted. This is just to indicate to a data user that all cells with “Budget 2008” or “Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland (SEAI) Grant Scheme” are related, in case they need to look more closely at them for analysis.

Actors: We record “actors” if a policy specifies that benefits are specific only to some actors (i.e. exclusively granted to households, companies, local governments, etc.). If there are not explicit guidelines this column is left blank.

Budget: If information is available, we record information on the total budget for the policy instrument. This is recorded in the columns “Government_budget” and “Government_budget_currency”.

Policy instruments for RE and EV support

In this section, we give an overview of the policy instruments that are being used to support renewable power generation and EV use in Germany, France, Ireland, and Greece.

Renewable power support policies

Accelerated Depreciation

Accelerated depreciation policy instruments are altered financial rules for renewable power projects, allowing them to depreciate (part of) the investment in the early years of the asset’s life, effectively reducing their taxable income during these years. For accelerated depreciation we record information on the depreciation period in years, and the share of investment affected. This policy instrument is mainly used in Ireland and France; Germany and Greece do not have special depreciation rules for renewable electricity technologies.

Feed-in Tariff (FIT)

Under a FIT, renewable power generators are paid a fixed sum of money for energy fed into the grid for a number of years. Sometimes, the tariff paid for new installations decreases (either per year or sometimes per month or quarter); the amount paid to an existing installation is not affected. This pre-defined rate of tariff decrease is called “degression”. In most cases, FITs are open to all new generators fulfilling the requirements, but sometimes the support is limited by an overall cap, limiting the total capacity supported by the policy. For FITs, we record the support level, degression and cap data (if applicable). FITs often have multiple conditions.

Many European FITs were phased out in 2016, leaving only very limited installations still eligible for support. We record data on small-scale support, but data users should pay careful **attention to the conditions columns** to understand which installations were eligible for FITs. For example, in 2017 France cancelled its FIT for solar PV over 100 kW but kept certain support measures for smaller installations. From 2022 onwards, it then reinstated FITs for solar PV between 100-500 kW in addition to keeping its support for smaller installations.

Feed-in Premium (FIP)

Renewable power generators are paid a premium on top of the price they achieve in the general electricity market, for electricity fed into the grid, for a number of years into the future. Sometimes, the premium paid to new installations decreases at a pre-defined rate (the degression). In most cases, premiums are open to all new generators fulfilling the requirements, but sometimes the support is limited by an overall cap, limiting the total capacity supported by the policy. For this instrument, we record information on the degression, unit of degression, cap, and until when the cap

is valid. Premiums are most often observed in Germany, for many different kinds of technologies; and in Ireland, for solar PV.

Auctions with FIT or FIP

In auctions with a FIT or FIP, governments put out tenders for specific amounts of capacity (or energy) which will be built which they will also support with an addition premium. Investors may bid on the amount they will build and the support amount that they will require. The selected bids are awarded support, usually a fixed tariff or a premium for a number of years. The instrument is thus often similar to FITs and Premiums, but differ in the qualification phase: only the winning bids are supported, whereas in FITs/Premiums all projects are (in principle) eligible for support.

Tenders may include a maximum level of support that a bidder can ask for. This is recorded in the “cap” column in the dataset. The outcome of the auction (weighted average support price that bidders will receive) is recorded under level_1. Further information on how we coded differences support levels among regions, actors, and technology characteristics can be found in the accompanying Metadata. In most cases, the awarded projects receive a fixed price tariff, although in some countries such as Germany it is a premium. The amount tendered and amount awarded are totaled per year, and the support level is averaged.

This instrument is common across countries, with many auctions taking place from 2000-present. The country with the least auctions is Ireland, which did not use this policy instrument between approximately 2003 and 2020.

Soft loans

With soft loans, the government (or or other government body) provides loans for renewable power projects at preferential conditions. In most cases, this is a lower interest rate than the market would provide, so as to lower the financing costs of new projects. The number of years refers to the maximum length of the loan rather than their actual duration.

So far, this instrument is mainly used in Germany and Ireland (with Irish support beginning more recently). However, Germany’s main institution which provides loans, the KfW, does not report information on their loan interest rates and how they change over time. Therefore, some loan data is merely indicative that the policies exist but we do not know their precise conditions.

Loan guarantee

With this instrument, governments seek to reduce the financing costs of new projects by guaranteeing to pay the loan should the project go bankrupt; this way, the required returns (on debt and/or equity) are lowered, because the default risk is lowered. The most relevant data for this instrument is the level, and the cap for the maximum size of the loan guarantee.

We did not find evidence of loan guarantees being used in our countries of interest. Germany has loan guarantees only for external projects with German company engagement (Racrestoff-UFK and KLIMA-UFK), which we do not record as our focus is on national transition policies. However, we know that Denmark uses these policy instruments; therefore, we include these policy instruments in the data gathering design to be updated for further countries in the future.

Tax incentives

Tax incentives refer to tax reductions (e.g. lower VAT rate for renewable power projects) and tax exemptions (e.g. a person buying a solar panel does not pay any VAT). For tax incentives, the most relevant data is on the level and conditions that must apply for exemptions.

All countries except Germany have various tax reductions and exemptions for renewable electricity; the most common types are income and investment tax reductions.

Subsidies (investment subsidies)

With an investment subsidy, governments pay part of the investment for renewable energy installation, so that the amount paid by the investor and effectively the project cost is decreased. For subsidies, the most relevant data is on the level and the cap. Subsidies are used in Ireland and Greece, mainly for small-scale renewable electricity generation between 2 and 1000 kWp.

Emission trading (“ETS”): cap-and-trade schemes

The instrument emission trading indirectly supports renewable power, as it makes carbon-intensive power generation relatively more expensive. We record data on mandatory cap-and-trade schemes. Our ETS cap-and-trade data are derived from ICAP.⁴ We record information on the prices for primary markets in “level_1” and for secondary markets in “level_2”. Emissions trading is coded as applying to “all renewables” as its technology type, as it makes them more competitive vis-à-vis fossil fuels. Supra- or subnational emissions trading systems, such as the European Emission Trading Scheme and the various US and Canadian emissions trading instruments are not included in this data, as they are not national-level policy instruments. So far, only Germany has its own emissions trading system, which was introduced in 2021 and only has a primary market, with prices increasing gradually. However we will continue to update this data for more countries, such as the UK which also has a secondary market.

Tradeable green certificates (TGCs)

With the introduction of a tradeable green certificates scheme, a government sets a long-term goal for the share of renewable power, and mandates all suppliers to obtain certificates as proof that they have bought sufficient amounts of renewables in their power mix. This way, a separate market for renewables certificates is created, leading to an additional revenue stream for renewable generators under the scheme. The quota amount is a regulatory instrument, which can also exist without a related market instrument: regulators can simply require entities to procure 50% of their power from renewables, without creating a trading scheme. At this stage we only gather data on the existence of trading schemes.

At this stage, Greece, Germany, France and Ireland do not have a TGS scheme. However because this is important for other countries such as Poland and Belgium which we will include in future updates, it is included in our data gathering scheme.

⁴ <https://icapcarbonaction.com/en>

Policy instruments for EV adoption support

Subsidies

We gather data on subsidies, where governments pay part of the cost for a given activity and therefore decrease the cost for other societal actors. These include subsidies for the purchase of EVs, the installation of personal or building charging infrastructure, and the installation of large-scale charging infrastructure. All countries incentivize EV purchases with subsidies for the acquisition of a new EV. Ireland was the first country to do so in 2011, followed by Germany, France, and Greece. In recent years most of the bonuses for EV purchasing have been reduced or cancelled, but there are still some subsidies for purchasing EV charging infrastructure such as wallboxes. In addition, some countries such as Ireland and Germany have programs to support the expansion of EV infrastructure by subsidizing companies and local governments/cities. For example in Ireland, the government covered up to EUR 5000 per charging point installed from 2019.

Tax incentives: tax rebates and exemptions

Tax incentives refer to tax reductions and tax exemptions (as above). In addition, we record information on sub-types, as there are many different kinds of taxation benefits available for EV purchasers. Tax incentives are present for all countries, and many were introduced relatively early on (for example in Ireland from 2010). Some incentives also become more stringent over time, eventually excluding hybrid vehicles to focus only on EVs. We find benefits including exemptions or reductions on the payments made on purchasing, the yearly taxes paid for vehicle ownership, and reductions in the taxable benefit-in-kind amounts for employees using company electric vehicles. As we investigate further countries this list may be expanded.

Fee decreases or exemptions

Fee decreases or exemptions are fiscal incentives where the government supports mitigation activities by reducing or exempting green activities from existing fees or charges (such as exempting EVs from paying highway tolls). So far we have seen examples of this in Ireland, but not for Germany, France and Greece. However, we know this is present in other European countries which will be added in the future.

Feebate or bonus-malus scheme

A feebate or bonus-malus scheme imposes fees on a high-emitting technology and provides rebates for low-emitting technologies. An emissions “null-point” is set, where the buyer gets neither a bonus nor a malus. The idea is that the system would be neutral on public finances. This is a well-established scheme in France, where its ambition (and complexity) has increased over time. As explained above, it was established in 2008 with 4 vehicle classes and rebates and has since been expanded to 72 vehicle classes. We observe that the stringency in terms of emissions requirements has increased significantly, as in 2008 the threshold for a fee began at 161 g CO₂/km and by 2023 was 123 g CO₂/km.

Soft loan

A soft loan is a loan provided by the government or a government body with preferential conditions to lower financing costs. As with the data for renewable power projects, it is difficult to find much detail on loan conditions. We therefore record as much information as possible, but may be missing data points on specific loan rates and duration. So far, we have only found evidence of soft loans in Germany from the year 2022. However, we expect with future updates to find more examples in other countries as this instrument is used for renewable electricity in Ireland as well (and possibly other European countries).

Tender with additional support

Government tenders for which investors bid to carry out (usually in this case the construction of charging infrastructure). These may be awarded some fixed amount of support for a number of years. So far, we find evidence of tenders for electric charging infrastructure that include support in Germany and France. This data is difficult to find, as there are not yet established auctions in most countries as is the case with renewable energy – it is often part of a policy package or strategy (and sometimes also done at the local level). In addition, the level of support is not usually published. We hope that in future updates this process will become more transparent.

Product retirement premium

A retirement premium for emissions-intensive products used by consumers such as fossil fuel vehicle swap or scrappage schemes. These are usually accompanied by conditions on which kinds of new vehicles make a person eligible to take advantage of the scheme: for example, the new vehicle they purchase must be an EV or PHEV. These are a popular instrument across countries and are usually used during economic recessions (i.e. in 2008/9 and 2020/1) as instruments to increase vehicle purchasing. Not all countries included specific environmental conditions in the first round of product retirement premiums: for example, Germany's 2009 policy only had the condition that the scrapped vehicle had to be 9 years old. More recent ones like Greece's 2020 scheme require that the scrapped vehicle be replaced with an EV, directly supporting the uptake of this technology vs. others like plug-in hybrids.

User behavior change

User change is a regulatory instrument that fosters changes in user behavior, for example by giving special (non-monetary) parking and driving benefits to EV owners. These are a common policy instrument in France, Germany, and Greece, where EV owners are given benefits such as better parking and the ability to use lanes that other cars cannot (such as bus or taxi lanes). Interestingly in Germany, these were granted already in 2015 before there were many monetary incentives for EV adoption.

Technology standards

A regulatory instrument that requires a specific technology, process or product. This can include phase-out mandates or bans of polluting technologies like ICE vehicles. Laws on the future ban on ICE sales were passed in Ireland and France in 2019. Ireland had originally planned with a phase-out date of 2030 and France of 2040. This was followed by a 2023 EU law which effectively bans the sale of

new fossil fuel combustion vehicles by 2035; therefore, France and Ireland will be obligated to align with the 2035 date (i.e. Ireland will also have to move its deadline up by 5 years). This also means that further countries should adopt similar bans in the years to come.

Remarks and Future Works

Remarks on the correctness and completeness of data

We have done everything we can to ensure the accuracy and completeness of our dataset, including multiple review rounds with several FAU STP group members. Yet, we cannot guarantee that all information is correct and complete. It is, to the best of our knowledge. Not all data points are readily available; although we cite them correctly, documents may hold incorrect data. In some cases, interpreting regulations is a non-trivial task, especially in different languages, and we do not always know each country's energy-political context and tradition. We refuse any liability for any errors or inaccuracies.

Future works

We plan to collect data for further countries, and keep updating our existing dataset. This is essential for robust international, intersectoral and cross-time evaluations of policy effectiveness; and to ensure that energy models that seek to include policy data can do so in the most up-to-date fashion (given the frequency with which policies often change). The next update round will include further European countries, with a focus on EU member states and the G20. We also hope to increase our collaboration with other research groups to extend our geographic coverage, and if possible our policy scope.

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